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THE NATIONAL LAW INSTITUTE UNIVERSITY
Kerwa Dam Road, Bhopal- 462 044 (M.P.)

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VOLUME – IX - XII (2017 - 2020)

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LIMITS OF EXPEDITING THE CRIMINAL TRIAL: SOME REFLECTIONS

Girjesh Shukla*

INTRODUCTION

In India, unabated growth in pendency of cases at various courts and delay in dispensation of justice is at alarming scale. As per the data provided by the government, 4.83 million cases are pending at various High Courts whereas pendency of cases at District Courts are 32.41 million.¹ Government, courts, commissions and academicians have offered many reasons behind the backlog of cases, ranging from frivolous litigation, adequacy of judges, facilities in the courts to procedural issues. The pendency of cases has affected the litigants adversely. The premises, where parties enter with a humble belief of *Satyamev Jayate* often gets miffed and rattled by delay in disposal. The failure is systemic, and no court can proclaim herself immune from this noxious disease. The faith in the judicial system is going abysmally low and the resultant symptoms are visible within and beyond the boundaries of these courts. While critiques remain puzzled with the delay and backlog of cases, the system holds 'speedy justice' a fundamental right for each citizen.

The concern about delay in disposal of cases, especially in criminal justice system, is not new. The process of reforming the criminal justice system and expediting the process has begun with the framing the Code of Criminal procedure, 1973, hereinafter referred as the Code of 1973. With the advent of Public Interest Litigation, the Supreme Court of India accelerated the process. With the beginning of new century, numerous modifications were inserted in the Code of

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¹ E-court Services, available at: https://ecourts.gov.in/ecourts_home/

Criminal Procedure, 1973 paving way to speedier process for the investigation and the trial.

It is often quoted that *justice delayed is justice denied*. In order to avoid delay in delivery of justice, reforms in the criminal justice system do focus around expediting the investigation and trial process. The Code of 1973, which replaced the earlier Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898, attempts were made to expedite the criminal justice system. Justice Malimath Committee Report deliberated on the issue of delay and recommended sweeping changes in the Procedure.² The law Commission of India has also dealt with the issue of delay. The Justice J.S. Verma Committee Report has also emphasized on the issue of delay and recommended certain categories of crime, especially crime against women to be taken up speedily to restore the belief of masses in the Criminal Justice System of India.

In the light of above, it can be said that speedy disposal of cases is the most important sign of a good and responsive criminal justice administration. People advocating speedy criminal justice systems argue for the expediting of entire process, beginning from investigation to the trial. The reasons behind expediting the process are many, which primarily revolve around the idea that delay in criminal justice process, either at the stage of investigation or the trial, adversely affects the outcome of the trial. Delay affects the process of collecting evidence, witnesses getting hostile and the victim being traumatized. Thus, the delay in judicial process sends a message to the victim, and thereby the society, that somewhere judicial system is failing to address their grievances.

In the present work, the author, without denying the need of having a swift and efficient criminal justice, argues for an effective criminal justice system wherein grievance of the parties should be at center-

² Committee on Reforms of Criminal Justice System, Government of India, Ministry of Home Affairs (2003), available at; https://www.mha.gov.in/sites/default/files/criminal_justice_system.pdf

stage, rather than the *disposal rate*. The work is fundamentally based theoretical premise '*justice hurried is justice buried*'. It is argued that belief of masses in the criminal justice system is, not about the *speed*, but the very *outcome* of a given trial. It is not the number of days or hours but fairness of system, which instill belief in the people. People's faith could be restored only when system is able to send a right message about its being fair. The work is divided into three parts. The part first of the paper narrates the concept of fairness in the investigation and trial process ensured by Code of 1973. In the second part of the work, data collected from the National Crime Record Bureau (NCRB) is examined as to whether making special provision about 'speedy trial' provides any *beneficial* outcome. Part third of the work provides a critical outlook towards accelerating the process without substantially modifying the court mechanism thereby adversely affecting the outcomes.

PART-I: CONCEPTUALIZING THE FAIR TRIAL-CODE OF 1973

CODE OF 1973: PROCEDURAL FAIRNESS

The formation of modern state under the *social contract theory* conceptualized by Thomas Hobbes, John Locke, and Jean-Jacques Rousseau, derives its validity on the fundamental premises that members of society have reason to endorse and comply with the fundamental social rules, laws, institutions, and/or principles of that society. And the primary reason behind endorsing the *social contract* was the *belief* that state will provide adequate protection to individual's right and liberties. The concomitant of this *belief* is as and when these rights or liberties will be intruded or transgressed, the state will provide effective remedy. And, while doing do, the state will treat each *party* to the *social contract* with utmost fairness.⁴

⁴ The Magna Carta of 1215, s. 39 reads as "No freeman shall be taken and imprisoned or disseized or exiled or in any way destroyed, nor will we go upon him

The principle of *fairness* in criminal justice system was very well received by International Community. With the development of contemporary human rights ideologies, the *fair trial* took the center-stage in criminal justice system. Article 10 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948 proclaims that '*everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him.*' Article 14 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966 provides that '*all persons shall be equal before the courts and tribunals. In the determination of any criminal charge against him, or of his rights and obligations in a suit at law, everyone shall be entitled to a fair and public hearing by a competent, independent and impartial tribunal established by law.*' It further provides the rule of '*presumption of innocence*' and guarantees '*natural justice*'.

The idea of *fairness* while taking up the matters relating to deprivation of life or liberties is fundamental principle enshrined in the Constitution of India.⁵ The Constitution of India *vide* Article 21 provides that "*No person shall be deprived of his life or liberties except according to the procedural established by law.*" Supreme Court of India while addressing the meaning and scope of the expression '*procedure established by law*', ruled that the procedure established under Article 21 should be just, fair, and reasonable.⁶ Further *such procedure* should be tested under Articles 14 and 19 of the Constitution.⁷ In the late 1980s, *doctrine of reasonableness*, legally as well as philosophically, was declared an essential element of equality or non-arbitrariness. It was observed that '*procedure*

nor send upon him, except by the lawful judgment of his peers and by the law of the land."

⁵ The Constitution of India, Article 14, 19, 21, 22.

⁶ *Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India*, AIR 1978 S.C. 597 (India); *See also*, *Sunil Batra v. Delhi Administration*, (1978) 4 S.C.C. 494 (India).

⁷ *Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India*, AIR 1978 S.C. 597 (India).

*contemplated by Article 21 must answer the test of reasonableness in order to be in conformity with Article 14. It must be "right and just and fair and not arbitrary, fanciful or oppressive; otherwise it would be no procedure at all and the requirement of Article '21 would not be satisfied."*⁸

In the light of above judicial pronouncements, it can be said that, within the precincts of Criminal Justice System, the *fair trial* is often associated with the 'rule of law', and thus it requires certain procedural compliances. The fundamental of these compliances are vis, natural justice, the presumption of innocence, right to a fair trial, the rule against double jeopardy, and the principle of legal equality. There have been incremental developments in these compliances such as prohibition against arbitrary arrest, use of violence to fetch involuntary confession to protect the rights of the accused. With greater focus on rights of victims, new additions are being added as part of *fair trial* wherein victim and her view is being taken seriously. Procedural safeguards are now available wherein victim cannot only participate in the process of trial, but also if aggrieved, can move to appellate jurisdiction on her own.

The statutory law dealing with the criminal trial too follows the philosophical idea behind above judicial pronouncements. Firstly, within the very adversarial system, the Code 1973 ensures "*the presiding judge must cease to be a spectator and a mere recording machine. He must become a participant in the trial by evincing intelligent active interest.*"⁹ In accordance with the provisions of the Code of 1973, and to ensure the fair trial, the court can exercise various powers. To illustrate a few, the power to direct the investigation,¹⁰ order for further investigation,¹¹ call for any party or

⁸ M.H. Hoskot v. State of Maharashtra, AIR 1978 S.C. 1548 (India).

⁹ Himanshu Singh Sabharwa v. State of M.P. [MANU/S.C./1193/2008].

¹⁰ The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973, s. 156(3).

¹¹ *Id.* at s. 173(8).

witness¹² or to call for material witness and procure the relevant documents¹³ so as to sub serve the cause of justice. With respect to regulating the dignity of parties, witnesses etc. the courts are equipped with additional power to regulate the court proceedings.¹⁴

The principle of 'fair trial' is expected to be observed by the trial court at each stage of the trial, and necessary powers & duties have been laid in the Code of 1973. Fairness in the judicial process is observed at every stage of the trial. The presumption of innocence is an accepted principle under the Code of 1973.¹⁵ Though, the courts are not oblivious of the fact that 'wrongful acquittals are undesirable and shake the confidence of the people in the judicial system', however 'much worse is the wrongful conviction of an innocent person'.¹⁶ Similarly, the principle of *autrefois acquit and autrefois convict* protects the ordinary person from being tried again for the same offence or on the same facts for any other offence.¹⁷ At the stage of trial, the Code of 1973 along with the judicial guidelines ensures natural justice,¹⁸ legal aid services,¹⁹ speedy trial.²⁰ The concepts of *double jeopardy*,²¹ right against self-incrimination,²² protects the individual from coercive state. Procedural fairness is further fortified *vide* various provisions at pre-trial stage i.e. during investigation, arrest and bail etc. The Code of 1973 provides special protection against illegal arrest.²³ A person arrested must be produced before a

¹² *Id.* at ss. 311 & 319.

¹³ The Indian Evidence Act, 1872, s. 165.

¹⁴ *Id.*

¹⁵ State of U.P. v. Naresh, (2001) 4 S.C.C. 324 (India).

¹⁶ Kali Ram v. State of H.P., (1973) 2 S.C.C. 808 (India).

¹⁷ Kolla Veera Raghav Rao v. Gorantla Venkateswara Rao., (2011) 2 S.C.C. 703 (India).

¹⁸ The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1873 ss. 207, 208, 273, 243, & 247.

¹⁹ Khatri v. State of Bihar, (1981) 1 SCC 635 (India); *See also*, Suk Das v. Union Territory of Arunachala Pradesh, (1986) 2 SCC 401 (India).

²⁰ Hussainara Khatoun v State of Bihar, AIR 1979 S.C. 1369 (India).

²¹ State of Andhra Pradesh v. Kokkiligadda Meerayya (1969) 1 S.C.C. 161 (India).

²² Selvi v State of Karnataka (2010) 7 S.C.C. 263 (India).

²³ The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 s. 50; *See also* Pranab Chatterjee v. State of Bihar, (1970) 3 SCC 926 (India).

Judicial Magistrate within 24 hours of arrest.²⁴ To discourage use of force against the accused while being in a police custody, the Indian Evidence Act, 1872 make certain types of confessionary statements inadmissible.²⁵ During investigation, the Investigating authority is required to prepared case diary,²⁶ which is subject to judicial scrutiny. An investigation is required to be completed efficiently and with promptness.²⁷ Judicial Officer's signature on each page of the case diary operates as a safeguard against manipulation and interpolation.

Finally, the procedural fairness, which play enormous role during the trial, is jealously guarded. Natural justice, which is part of Article 14, the Constitution of India, is the principle underpinning the entire trial. The procedure ensures that the rights of accused, rights of victim, & dignity of witnesses are not compromised during the trial;²⁸ and at the same time, court is empowered & expected to dispose the case swiftly.²⁹ The court is empowered enough to discover the truth,³⁰ and deliver a just decision³¹ along with the reasons.³² A copy of the judgment is required to be supplied to the parties to the case that will ensure transparency behind final verdict of the judge which will instill trust & confidence in all stakeholders.³³

The Supreme Court of India observed that "each one has an inbuilt right to be dealt with fairly in a criminal trial. Denial of a fair trial is

²⁴ *Id* at s. 57; See also *State of Punjab v. Ajaib Singh*, AIR 1953 S.C. 10 (India); *Joginder Kumar v. State of Uttar Pradesh* (1994) 4 SCC 260 (India); *D.K. Basu v. State of West Bengal*, (1997) 1 S.C.C. 416 (India); *Arnesh Kumar v. State of Bihar*, Criminal Appeal No. 1277 of 2014 (S.C.) (India).

²⁵ The Indian Evidence Act, 1872, s. 25.

²⁶ The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973, s. 172 & 173.

²⁷ *Id.* at Ss. 57, & 167; *See also*, *Bhagwant Singh v. Commissioner of Police, Delhi*, AIR 1985 SC 1285.

²⁸ *Id.* at Ss. 479 & 327.

²⁹ *Id.* 309.

³⁰ *supra* note 13.

³¹ The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 Ss. 311, 319.

³² *Id.* at s. 354.

³³ *Id.*

as much injustice to the accused as it is to the victim and to society.³⁴ The same is ensured through statutory provisions laid down in the Code of 1973 as referred herein above. All expectations lie with the trial courts that how & to what extent they would ensure speedy disposal of cases without harming the basic tenet of 'fair trial'.

PART-II: SPEEDY TRIAL- A REQUIREMENT OF FAIR TRAIL

Speedy trial is recognised as fundamental rule of fair trial.³⁵ This recognition is given by United Nations as well. Article 9(3) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966 provides that any one arrested or detained on a criminal charge *shall be brought promptly before a Judge or other officer authorised by law to exercise judicial power and shall be entitled to trial within a reasonable time or to release.* Article 14(3)(c), further guarantees every [accused] a right 'to be tried without undue delay.' US Constitution *vide* the sixth amendment inserted explicit provision about 'speedy trial' in criminal matter and has been attributed to 'due process'.³⁶ It is to be noted that these conventions are not a dead letter. It may further be noted that Supreme Court of India has used these international standards for carving out new jurisprudence and thereby expanded the horizon of protection not only to the accused but also to victim of crime.³⁷

³⁴ *Zahira Habibullah Sheikh v. State of Gujarat*, (2006) 3 SCC 374 (India).

³⁵ *Hussainara Khatton (I) v. State of Bihar*, [1979] 5 S.C.R. 169 (India); *Kadra Pehdiya (I) v. State of Bihar*, AIR 1981 S.C. 939 (India); *Kadra Pehdiya (II) v. State of Bihar*, AIR 1982 S.C. 1167 (India); *State of Maharashtra v. Champa Lal Punjaji Shah*, [1981] 3 S.C.R. 610 (India). In foreign jurisdictions also, where the right to a fair trial within a reasonable time is a constitutionally protected right, the infringement of that right has been held in appropriate cases sufficient to quash a conviction or to stop further proceedings: *Strunk v. United States*, 37 Law Ed. 2d 56; *Barkar v. Wingo*, 407 US 514; *Bell v. Director of Public Prosecutions, Jamaica*, [1985] (II) All ER 585.

³⁶ *Kolfer v. NCardina* (1967) 396 U.S. 213.

³⁷ *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan*, (1997) 6 S.C.C. 241 (India), the Supreme Court of India observed: "The International Conventions and norms are to be read into them in the absence of enacted domestic law occupying the fields when there is no inconsistency between them." *See also, Nilabati Behera v. State of Orissa*, [(1993) 2

A comprehensive reading of certain provision of the Code of 1973 makes it abundantly clear that 'speedy trial' is a fundamental premise over which the idea of fair trial is based. To be precise on this issue, some of these provisions needs to be highlighted. In fact, in *Abdul Rehman Antulay v. R.S. Nayak*,³⁸ the Constitution Bench stated that 'right to speedy trial flowing from Article 21 encompasses all the stages, namely the stage of investigation, inquiry, trial, appeal, revision and re-trial.'

SPEEDY INVESTIGATION

A close reading of provisions contained in the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 inevitably reveals that swift and effective investigation is cardinal to criminal process. Chapter XII, titled as "Information to the Police and their Powers to Investigate" lays down general rules for Investigation. As per Section 157, the officer in charge of the police station, after receiving an information as to the commission of an offence, of which he is empowered to investigate under section 156, he shall forthwith send a report of the same to judicial Magistrate and "*shall proceed in person ...to the spot, to investigate the facts and circumstances of the case.*" However, proviso attached with this Section relax this sense of urgency. It provides, *firstly*, that cases where name information contains name of accused and *the offence is not serious in nature*, the Investigating Officer may not proceed to spot, and rather use the power of Section 160 & 161 to call all persons including accused to Police Station. Secondly, cases where it appears that *there is no sufficient ground for entering on an investigation*, Investigating Officer shall not investigate the case. However, 157(2) makes it categorical that in either of these two situations, the Investigating Officer shall state in his 'report' about the

SCC 746] where the court said that 'there is no reason why these International Conventions and norms could not be used for construing the fundamental rights expressly guaranteed in the Constitution of India.'

³⁸ *Abdul Rehman Antulay v. R.S. Nayak*, and another (1992) 1 S.C.C. 225 (India).

'reasons' for not fully complying with the requirements of 'proceeding for spot investigation' or 'not entering into investigation,' as the case may be. The 'report' filed to the Magistrate provides a way by which effective investigation is insured.

Another interesting provision would be Section 167 along with Section 57 of the Code of 1973. 167. Though, Section 167 essentially deals with different types of custody, and provision for default bail, still the opening line of the provision could be taken as a hint towards speedy investigation. The opening line of section 167 reads as "whenever any person is arrested and detained in custody and it appears that the investigation cannot be completed within the period of twenty-four hours fixed by section 57..." Again, Section 167(2) makes it mandatory for the Court to release the accuse on bail, if the investigation does not complete within the 60 or 90 days as the case may be, and no police report is filed within these stipulated period.³⁹ The effect of the new proviso is to entitle an accused person to be released on bail if the investigating agency fails to complete the investigation within 60 days. Reading these expressions along with the mandate contained in Section 57 of the Code of 1973, the policy of 'speedy investigation' would be the only logical conclusion.

The Supreme Court has taken a stern view, if it is found that the investigating team has failed to comply with the time limit prescribed in provisions as referred hereinabove. Whenever it has notice that there has been a grave failure on part of the investigating team, courts have protected rights of the accused. Like, in *State of Uttar Pradesh v. Parashottam*,⁴⁰ Supreme Court quashed the police charge sheet for an offence under Section 120B and 420 of Indian Penal Code, 1860, submitted after a gap of 17 years, while observing that "whatever may be the reason, the fact remains that prosecution is pending in this case

³⁹ *Natabar Parida v. State of Orissa*, AIR 1975 S.C. 1465 (India); *Bashir v. State of Haryana*, (1977) 4 SCC 410. (India); *Raghubir Singh v. State of Bihar*, AIR 1987 SC 149 (India).

⁴⁰ *State of Uttar Pradesh v. Parashottam*, AIR 1991 SC 1015 (India).

over three decades and even the trial has not as yet commenced. It would be travesty of justice if we permit the prosecution to continue.” Supreme Court in *State of Andhra Pradesh v. P.V. Pavithran*⁴¹, had examined the issue of delay in investigation, and if it could serve as a sufficient ground for quashing the proceedings. The Court had admitted the fact that lethargic and lackadaisical manner of investigation over a prolonged period compel the accused to live under extreme emotional and mental stress. However, the Apex Court has pointed out that ‘there are offences of grave magnitude, which would necessarily involve considerable time for unearthing the crimes and bringing the culprits to book. *Therefore, it is not possible to formulate inflexible guidelines or rigid principles of uniform application for speedy investigation or to stipulate any arbitrary period of limitation within which investigation in a criminal case should be completed.*’ It has further stated that whether or not the delay in investigation violated fair trial principle, would depend on ‘*various factors including whether such delay was unreasonably long or caused deliberately or intentionally to hamper the defence of the accused or whether such delay was inevitable in the nature of things or whether it was due to the dilatory tactics adopted by the accused. The Court, in addition, has to consider whether such delay on the part of the investigating agency has caused grave prejudice or disadvantage to the accused.*’

What is noticeable here is that the Court was not oblivious of the fact that delay in investigation is inherently part of the process, and thus, the delay in investigation *ipso facto* does not violate principles of fair trial.

⁴¹ AIR 1990 SC 1266; See also *Raghubir Singh v. State of Bihar*, [1986] 4 S.C.C. 481 (India).

SPEEDY TRIAL

Fair, just and reasonable procedure implicit in Article 21 of the Constitution creates a right in the accused to be tried speedily.⁴² The rule of speedy trial is imbibed in the Code of criminal Procedure, 1973. Directly or indirectly, provisions contained in the Code inevitably suggest for speedy disposal of cases.

Provision enabling the court to discharge the accused even before entering upon defence evidence state,⁴³ or acquit him before entering upon defence evidence⁴⁴ are indirectly serving the purpose of speedy trial. By virtue of this provision, the trial judge has [judicial] discretion to consider as pace of criminal proceeding. Whereas, section 309 of the Code could be taken as direct rule expediting the trial process. This section provides that “*in every inquiry or trial, the proceedings shall be held as expeditiously as possible, and in particular, when the examination of witnesses has once begun, the same shall be continued from day to day until all the witnesses in attendance have been examined, unless the Court finds the adjournment of the same beyond the following day to be necessary for reasons to be recorded.*” This section further provides that where the Magistrate finds it necessary to postpone the commencement of, or adjourn, any inquiry or trial, he may do so but only for reasonable period.

In furtherance of objective behind above referred provisions, the Supreme Court has issued directions from time to time. For having proper court management, expediting the trial, Supreme Court in *State of Kerala v. Rasheed*,⁴⁵ has directed all the trial courts to prepare a detailed case-calendar at the commencement of the trial, scheduling

⁴² Abdul Rehman Antulay v. R.S. Nayak, and another (1992) 1 SCC 225 (India); *See also*, Kartar Singh v. State of Punjab, (1994) 3 S.C.C. 569 (India).

⁴³ The Code of Criminal procedure, 1973, Ss. 227, 239.

⁴⁴ *Id.* s. 232.

⁴⁵ AIR 2019 SC 721.

the dates for examination of witnesses; the proposed order of production of witnesses; expected time required for examination of witnesses; availability of witnesses at the relevant time, etc. Court further directed that, as far as possible, the request for deferral under Section 231(2) of the Code must be preferably made before the preparation of the case calendar. The case-calendar, prepared in accordance with the above guidelines, must be followed strictly, unless departure from the same becomes necessary.

Irrespective of these provisions, there are cases pending since long in various courts. Numerous reasons are being cited for the delay. It would be unfair to blame any individual cause such as court management, prosecution, or the accused. The causes of delay are inherent to the very nature of the criminal proceeding. This ranges from nature of offence, number of accused, deliberate tactics by accused or prosecution, backlog of cases in the trial court, and court management etc. In *Abdul Rehman Antulay v. R.S. Nayak*,⁴⁶ the Constitution bench, while dealing with the with the issue of delay and fair trial, had suggested to handle the question of delay from procedural perspective, and suggested to minimize the incarceration before conviction etc. The Court had cautioned that while determining whether undue delay has occurred or not, one must have regard to all the attendant circumstances, including nature of offence, number of accused and witnesses, the workload of the court concerned, prevailing local conditions and so on- what is called, the systemic delays. With respect to delayed trial and escalated cost of judicial administration, Supreme Court stated that 'financial constraints and priorities in expenditure would not enable the Government to avoid its duty to ensure speedy trial to the accused.'⁴⁷ Courts have taken serious view about the fact that the prosecution, in certain cases, deliberately adopt delaying tactics to keep the accused persons in jail as long as possible and to harass them particularly when the evidence is of a

⁴⁶ *Abdul Rehman Antulay v. R.S. Nayak*, (1992) 1 S.C.C. 225 (India).

⁴⁷ *Hussainara Khatoun and others (IV) v. Home Secretary, State of Bihar*, (1980) 1 S.C.C 98 (India).

weak character and the conviction is not a probable result.⁴⁸ In *Madhu Mehta v. Union of India*,⁴⁹ Supreme Court commuted the death sentence to life imprisonment based on inordinate delay.

However, whether delay should result into quashing of trial or not is moot question over which courts have deliberated very cautiously. It is settled law that a delayed trial is not necessarily an unfair trial, as the delay might have occasioned by accused or the very fact and circumstances of the case. Thus, there could be no fixed period of delay which could be considered decisive in quashing delayed trials.

While examining the post-indictment proceedings, one need to be cautious about the scope and limits of speedy trial. A minor deviation from the established procedure may result into severe compromise with the rights of accused and victims, equally. The quality of justice would be first casualty if the cardinal rules that are inherent to the 'natural justice' are being squeezed to accelerate the proceedings.

PART-III PRINCIPLES OF SPEEDY TRIAL – PRACTICES AS REFLECTED FROM NCRB REPORT

In the recent past, concern about backlog of cases has created huge uproar amongst masses. After horrendous Nirbhaya Gang Rape (2013), Justice Verma committee had suggested for time-schedule for conducting investigation and trial. States, like Andhra Pradesh, has introduced amendments whereby specified time schedule is fixed for investigation and trial of certain offences.

The process of making statutory rule for time bound investigation and trial seems to have gained momentum after notification of the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2018, whereby various provisions of Code of 1973 are amended to prescribed speedy criminal process. By the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2018, Section 173(1A) is

⁴⁸ State of Maharashtra v. Champalal Punjaji Shan, (1981) 3 S.C.C. 610 (India).

⁴⁹ Madhu Mehta v. Union of India, (1989) 4 S.C.C. 62 (India).

amended and now, offences under sections 376, 376A, 376AB, 376B, 376C, 376D, 376DA, 376DB or 376E of the Indian Penal Code are required to be completed within two months. Proviso attached to Section 309(1) of CrPC is also amended with an effect that 'when the inquiry or trial relates to an offence under section 376, 376A, 376AB, 376B, 376C, 376D, 376DA 376DB of the Indian Penal Code, 1860 the inquiry or trial shall be completed within a period of two months from the date of filing of the charge sheet. With respect to these offences, a new sub-section (4) is inserted in Section 374, which provides that appeal in such cases shall be disposed of within a period of six months from the date of filing of such appeal.

Andhra Pradesh Legislature has passed the Andhra Pradesh Disha Act-Criminal Law (Andhra Pradesh) Amendment Bill, 2019 whereby Section 173 of the CrPC is amended by inserting Section 173 (1B). According to newly proposed law, where an offence is committed under either of Section 354F, 354G, 376, 376A, 376AB, 376D, 376 DA, 376DB, and 376E of Indian Penal Code, 1860, and where conclusive evidence is there, the investigation shall be completed within seven days from the date of receipt of information. By inserting an amendment in Section 309, the Bill proposed to complete the trial with 14 working days from the date of filing of charge sheet. Similarly, appeal in such matters shall be disposed of within 45 days from the date of filing of appeal.

Recently, the Department-Related Parliamentary Standing Committee on Human Resource Development in its 316th Report (March 2020), while recommending for strengthening of law relating to women, has suggested for fixing a time frame for deciding cases of gender-based violence against women. Committee felt that 'necessary amendments should be made for filing of charge sheet in all such cases within 30

days, denying bail to the accused and expediting the disposal of pending cases within 6 months.⁵⁰

There is no doubt that these mandatory time-bound rules of trial will expedite the trial process and will fulfill the demand of having *speedy trial*. But whether it will produce 'speedy justice' is yet to be assessed.

It would be too early to predict about these amendments and its impact. However, these amendments need to be taken up cautiously. This need to be examined critically to dispel the possibility of *justice hurried is justice buried*. Since, the experience from the past often provides sign for the future, it would not be improper to explore the data released by NCRB to assess the overenthusiastic demands of *speedy trial*.

DATA PRESENTATION

Efficient investigative machinery with fully equipped with necessary infrastructure is the prerequisite of speedy trial. Does providing a mandatory time schedule would serve the purpose of achieving speedy trial? This work is based on the fundamental premises that investigation agency, having freedom as to the manner and time-space for completing investigation, will be more effective in producing adequate evidence, which in turn will improve the rate of conviction. A mandatory time bound investigation will develop a tendency to bundle the investigation within the deadline, and thus, the quality of such investigation, and the rate of conviction both will be adversely affected.

Since, providing time-bound investigated is more often seen with violence against women, especially rape cases, researcher randomly collected data about the number/rate of conviction and acquittal in three different categories of offences i.e. Murder & Kidnapping and

⁵⁰ Presented to the Rajya Sabha on 19th March 2020, and laid on the Table of Lok Sabha on 19th March, 2020.

Rape, since the year 1985. The rate of conviction is examined in the light of data on investigation i.e. total disposal of cases and the number of charge sheet filed. The purpose is to explore as whether the cases investigated by police in any given year, and the number of charge sheet filed finds any correlation between rate of conviction? It was the year 1985 from where the NCRB started providing comprehensive data especially on offence of rape. The data collected is tabulated as under-

Table-01: Disposal of Cases by Court

Year	Murder				Rape				Kidnapping			
	Conviction		Acquittal		Conviction		Acquittal		Conviction		Acquittal	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
1985	6339	42.5	8586	57.5	1591	39	2487	61	2041	35.8	3691	35.8
1990	6337	41.3	8997	58.7	2566	41.5	3611	58.5	2119	31.6	4586	31.6
2000	8397	35.6	15157	64.4	3133	29.8	7385	70.2	3177	29.5	7597	29.5
2005	9329	34.6	17620	65.4	3645	25.4	10670	74.6	2546	24.4	7849	24.4
2010	8383	36.7	14337	63.3	3788	26.6	10475	73.4	3870	27.7	10090	27.7
2015	7763	39.5	11879	60.5	5514	29.4	13250	70.6	4175	23.9	13276	23.9
2018	7512	41.4	10653	58.6	4708	27.2	12605	72.8	4973	29.2	12058	29.2

Table- 02: Investigation Status*

Year	Murder		Rape		Kidnapping	
	Disposal Rate	Charge-Sheet Rate**	Disposal Rate	Charge-Sheet Rate**	Disposal Rate	Charge-Sheet Rate**
1985	68.8	81.3	73.8	88.5	70.7	77.7
1990	61.8	61.5	71.7	71.5	67.3	66.8
1995	65.7	78.3	72.9	90.8	65.9	72.3
2000	64.5	64.2	72.9	72.8	63.2	62.9
2005	59.6	84.7	69.3	84.7	69.3	56.8
2010	53.7	84.2	64.2	94.5	42.8	72.4
2015	59	86.2	68.2	96.1	57.2	68
2018	60.6	84.2	70.9	85.3	61.9	39.8

*NCRB provides charge sheeting rate from the year 2015 onwards, which stands for: Total number of Cases Charge sheeted / Total cases disposed of by Police*100

** Charge-sheet Rate is charge-sheet filed against total completed investigation.

It may be noted that the conviction rate (Table-01) for offence like murder remained substantially same during years 1985 to 2018 i.e. between 42.5% and 34.6%. The deviation in rate of conviction is only of 7.9%. Similarly, in the same span period, the rate of conviction in case of kidnapping is also between 35.8% to 23.9%, with a deviation 11.9%. However, from the year 1985 to 2018, the conviction rate in case of offence of rape fluctuated between 41.5% to 25.4% i.e. with a highest deviation (16.1%). It is clear from the data that regardless of sensitization towards offences against women, there is a sharp decline in the conviction rate since the year 1985 (39%). Again, if the data is examined from the far ends of this span period i.e. between 1985 and 2018, it provides disturbing trend. The difference between the rate of conviction for murder in 1985 (42%) and in 2018 (41.4%) is of 0.6%. Whereas, in case of offence of rape, the rate of conviction in 1985 was 39% and in 2018 it came down to mere 27.2%, with a huge fall of 11.8%.

This data is required to be further analyzed in the light of rate of filing of charge sheet (Table-02). The data on disposal of investigation cases by police and the filing of charge sheet reflects that unlike the conviction rate, which is having downward movement for rape cases (Table-01), the rate of filing of charge sheet is extremely high (Table - 02). The data on disposal and charge-sheeting suggests that rate of disposing investigation regarding offences of rape is as high as 96%. As per the data collected, between the year 1985 to 2018, the mean value of disposal of investigations of murder cases is 61.71%, whereas for offence of rape, the mean value is 70.4% i.e. much higher. Similarly, during the period 1985 to 2018, the mean value of rate of charge-sheeting is 78%, for offence of murder, whereas for the offence of rape, it is 85.5%. Thus, high mean value of investigation (70.4%) along with much higher rate of charge-sheeting (85.5%) in the matters relating to rape, while having extremely poor conviction rate (mean value 31.2%) suggests some form of anomaly.

What could be the reasons behind this type of outcome? It may be noted here that, it was around 1990 when people became vocal about expediting certain types of crimes, specially crime against women. In the wake of many judicial guidelines, remarks by statutory Institutions like National Human Right Commission, National Women Commission etc. these issues were raised vociferously at various forums. Misconstrued idea of expediting investigation without having efficient police administration with enhanced capabilities, the police department started filing of the charge sheet hurriedly. This is submitted that, in addition to all other all other reasons, the current approach of expediting the investigation (mandatory time schedule) and filing of charge sheet could be one of the reasons behind such as low rate of conviction in rape cases.

The author does not mean to suggest that low rate of conviction leads to failure of justice. The idea is to bring an anomaly in opinion of three components of criminal justice administration viz, investigating authority, the prosecution, and the trial court. It is to be pointed out

that when the investigating authority submits the charge-sheet, it submits its opinion that accused has committed the offence. Similarly, when the prosecution opens the case by proposing the charge, it means that in the opinion of prosecution the accused has committed offence. Further, when the court frames charge, it is confirmation that, in the opinion of the court the accused, *prima facie*, has committed the offence. But, when the trial court delivers the verdict, stating that the accused has not committed the offence, it means there was stark difference in opinions at two levels, (i) opinion of the trial court at charge stage and at the time of final verdict, & (ii) opinion of the investigation authority & prosecution and the trial court. If this variation is observed through data i.e. the mean value of rate of charge-sheeting (95% for rape cases) and the mean value of data on conviction (31.2% for rape cases), it clearly suggests serious anomalies in the very functioning of the criminal justice administration.

CONCLUSION

This paper has examined the idea of speedy trial from a quite different perspective. As argued in the beginning, speedy trial is not necessarily a *fair trial*. Accelerating the investigation process or the trial may not produce desirable outcome i.e. delivery of justice. The NCRB data clearly suggests that desire of speedy trial need to be approached cautiously, otherwise it may end up in another disaster. In this regard, the recent trends suggest that the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2018, or Disha Act, 2019 need to be approached critically and cautiously. It is submitted that speedy justice requires be re-conceptualized. It will begin by creating separate and professional investigation unit for each Session Division, redesigning the categories of offences under Code of 1973, so as to redistribute the trial of cases amongst different categories of courts, and instilling professional approach in prosecutors and benches for handling the case at various level. Many provisions of the Code of 1973 that are

until now a dead letter need to be exercised by trial courts for better outcome.

There is no doubt that denial of *speedy trial* will cause severe damage to the victim as well as to the accused. But, a trial, howsoever speedy it may be, if it results into a disastrous outcome or struck into longstanding battle for appeals and revisions, the damaged cause would be irreparable and long lasting.

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